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ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: FROM TEACHING TO LEARNING, A PEDAGOGICAL REFLECTION

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ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is still seeking greater space in teaching and learning, even with the growing academic debate, there is still a need for ethical legitimization, this challenge will still depend on a development on the subject, through incentives and investments in technology. Given this scenario, what are the thoughts on artificial intelligence in teaching and learning? The general aim of this study was therefore to carry out a literature review on artificial intelligence in teaching and learning. The research was bibliographical with a qualitative approach, seeking to bring a reflection on the subject. We found that artificial intelligence is advancing in the academic context, but that there are still difficulties in implementing it, due to ethical issues and technological development. We conclude that pedagogical reflection must be continuous, as AI is an essential tool.